

tion (usually 3 different concentrations). In the measurement of the metal ion concentration, standard deviation was found to be 0.05 to 0.07 ppm and percentage relative error was found to be 0.1-0.3%.

A comparative study with other reagents, recently used for the metals under study (Table 2) was undertaken and it was found that the BHMAH is a better reagent.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi for award of a Senior Research Fellowship to one of them (S.R.M.).

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Use of 2-Hydroxy-4-Ethoxyacetophenone Oxime (HEAO) as Analytical Reagent : Studies on Nickel Chelate

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Manuscript received 4 March 1980, revised 28 June 1982,
accepted 28 January 1983

MANY reagents¹⁻³ have been used for the determination of nickel. In continuation of our work on the use of 2-hydroxy-4-ethoxyacetophenone oxime (HEAO) as a reagent for copper⁴, we have used it as a gravimetric reagent for nickel.

The reagent gives green precipitate of nickel chelate quantitatively in the pH range 5.5 to 9.0. The chelate is insoluble in alcohol, ether and acetic acid but is soluble in chloroform. There are advantages in using this reagent over other reagents⁴.

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Determination of nickel : Gravimetric determination of nickel in different aliquots at pH 5.5-6.0 was carried out according to the method described earlier⁴. The error in any case did not exceed $\pm 0.3\%$.

Cations like Zn(II), Pb(II), Cd(II), Sr(II), Mg(II), Mn(II) and Al(III) and anions like chloride, nitrate, bromide, sulphate, tartrate and citrate were found not to interfere in the gravimetric determination of nickel at pH 5.5-6.0. The error in any case was not greater than $\pm 0.7\%$. The interference due to Fe(II) and Fe(III) was removed using sequestering agents like potassium citrate or Rochelle salt. Co(II) chelate coprecipitates with nickel chelate at pH 6.0, but as the cobalt chelate is soluble in alcohol it can be removed during washing of the nickel chelate with alcohol. The reagent was used to determine copper(II) and nickel(II) in binary mixture by working at controlled pH. The results were reproducible.

Structure of nickel chelate : The nickel chelate was analysed for carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and metal content. The results correspond to $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3\text{N})_2$. Metal to ligand ratio of 1 : 2 was also confirmed by Job's method of continuous variation.

The visible spectra of nickel chelate in chloroform gives a strong band at 375 nm. Nickel chelate was found to be diamagnetic showing the absence of unpaired electron. Ni(II) has d^8 configuration and hence it conforms to square planar structure.

IR spectra of nickel chelate shows the band at $2900-3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (=N-OH group). The band appearing at 3400 cm^{-1} (phenolic -OH group) in oxime disappeared in chelate. The bands due to $\nu\text{ C}=\text{N}$ and $\nu\text{ NO}$ appeared at lower frequency in chelate than those in ligand⁵.

On the basis of the above evidences the following structure is suggested for the nickel chelate.

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